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Subsequential Convergence in Locally Convex Spaces

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Abstract :

Given a locally convex Hausdorff linear topological space, we will construct the finest Locally convex topology with the same sequentially compact sets as the initial topology.

Keywords : Locally convex space, Subsequential neighborhood of zero, subsequential space, Sequentially compact set

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1. Introduction :

It is evergreen problem in topology whether it is possible to construct a finest topology without disturbing the character of initial topology. Such a problem was studied by J.H. Webb[6], which prompted us to construct a finest locally convex topology, which has the same sequentially compact sets as the initial topology. Here it may be mentioned that pre-compact sets need not be sequentially compact but converse is true and hence our construction is a more general version of J.H. Webb. We have also examined completeness of $X^\oplus$ with respect to topology generated by class of bounded subsets of X .

By X we designate a fixed locally convex topological vector space.

$$X^* = \text{Algebraic dual of } X$$

$$X' = (X, \tau)' = \text{Topological dual of } X.$$

$$X^b = (X, \tau)^b = \{f \in X^* : \sup_{x \in B} |f(x)| < \infty \text{ for all } \tau\text{-bounded } B \subset X\}$$

$$\begin{aligned} X^+ &= (X, \tau)^+ = \text{sequential dual of } X \\ &= \{f \in X^* : f(x) \rightarrow 0 \text{ for all } \tau \text{ null } \{x_n\}\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} X^\oplus &= (X, \tau)^\oplus = \text{subsequential dual of } X \\ &= \{f \in X^* : |f(x_{nk})| \rightarrow 0 \text{ for all } \tau \text{ null } \{x_{nk}\}\} \end{aligned}$$

Then clearly $X' \subset X^+ \subset X^\oplus \subset X^b \subset X^*$.

2. Sequentially Compact :

A set M is called sequentially compact if every sequence of points of M contains a subsequence which is convergent to a point of M .

Now, we will construct the finest locally topology on X with the same sequentially compact sets as the initial topology τ , and e will denote this by τ^s . Two constructions are possible one internal and other external.

2.1 Proposition : Let (X, τ) be a locally convex space and S denote the class of all τ -sequentially compact subsets of X . Let U be the class of all absolutely convex subsets of X , with the condition that $\forall S \in S$, there exist finite number of points $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n$ in S such that

$$S \subseteq \cup_{i=1}^n (x_i + V) \text{ then,}$$

- (i) $V \in U \Rightarrow \alpha V \in U, \forall \alpha$
- (ii) Every $V \in U$ is absorbent

(iii) U is closed under finite intersection.

Proof : (i) As $S \subseteq \cup_{i=1}^n (x_i + V)$ then since S is τ -sequential compact subset therefore αS is also τ -sequentially compact. Hence $\alpha S \subseteq \cup_{i=1}^n (x_i + \alpha V)$.

Which implies that $\alpha V \in U$.

(ii) Let $V \in U$ and $x \in X$, consider the set $A = \{\alpha x : |\alpha| \leq 1\}$ which is a member of S . A is contained in $\cup_{i=1}^n (\alpha_i x + V)$ where $\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_n$ are scalars such that $|\alpha_i| \leq 1$, i.e., $A \subseteq \cup_{i=1}^n (\alpha_i x + V)$. If α_0 is any other scalar such that $|\alpha_0| \leq 1$ and $\alpha_0 \neq \alpha_i$ (for $i=1$ to n). Then $\alpha_0 x \in A$.

$$\text{So, } \alpha_0 x \in \cup_{i=1}^n (\alpha_i x + V)$$

$$\Rightarrow \alpha_0 x \in (\alpha_j x + V) \text{ for some } j$$

$$\Rightarrow \alpha_0 x - \alpha_j x \in V$$

$$\Rightarrow x \in (\alpha_j - \alpha_0)^{-1} V, \text{ As } V \text{ is balanced so } V \text{ absorbs } x.$$

(iii) Let V_1 and $V_2 \in U$, then $V_1 \cap V_2$ is absolutely convex. Let $S \in S$, then there exists points $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_m, y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n$ in S such that,

$$S \subseteq \cup_{i=1}^n (x_i + V_1) \text{ and } S \subseteq \cup_{j=1}^n (y_j + V_2),$$

$$\text{So, } S \subseteq \cup_{i,j} (x_i + V_1) \cap (y_j + V_2)$$

Now $z_{ij} \in S \cap (x_i + V_1) \cap (y_j + V_2)$ for some i and j

$$\Rightarrow z_{ij} - x_i \in V_1 \text{ and } z_{ij} - y_j \in V_2 \quad (1)$$

$$\text{If } z \in (x_i + V_1) \cap (y_j + V_2)$$

$$\Rightarrow z - x_i \in V_1 \text{ and } z - y_j \in V_2 \quad (2)$$

as V_1 and V_2 are absolutely convex thus,

$$\Rightarrow z - z_{ij} \in 2V_1 \text{ and } z - z_{ij} \in 2V_2$$

$$\Rightarrow z - z_{ij} \in 2(V_1 \cap V_2)$$

$$\Rightarrow z \in z_{ij} + 2(V_1 \cap V_2)$$

$$\Rightarrow S \subseteq \cup_{i,j} (z_{ij} + 2(V_1 \cap V_2)), \text{ so } (V_1 \cap V_2) \in U$$

Take U as a base at 0 for a locally topology on X , which is denoted by τ^s , then $\tau \leq \tau^s$. Now by definition every τ^s -sequentially compact subset of X is τ -sequentially compact and every τ -sequentially compact subset of X is τ^s -sequentially compact, so the topologies τ and τ^s have the same sequentially compact sets on X .

3. External Construction of τ^s :

3.1 Proposition : Let $\langle X, Y \rangle$ be a dual pair of linear spaces. Let δ be a class of $\sigma(X, Y)$ -closed subsets of X generating on Y . The topology τ_n of uniform convergence of members of η , then following statements are equivalent.

(a) Each $M \in \delta$ is τ_n -sequentially compact in X .

(b) Each $N \in \eta$ is τ_δ -sequentially compact in Y .

Proof : It immediately follows from the fact that sequentially compact set is closed.

3.2 Lemma : Let (X, τ) be a locally convex space, then

$$(i) X^c = \{f \in X^* : \sup_{x \in S} |f(x)| < \infty \text{ for every } S \in \mathcal{S}\}$$

(ii) If τ_1 is another locally convex topology on X such that τ and τ_1 have the same sequentially compact sets in X then τ and τ_1 have the same closed sets in X .

Proof : (i) Every mackey convergent sequence is sequentially compact sets in X , then τ and τ_1 have the same closed sets in X .

(ii) By (i), $(X, \tau)^c = (X, \tau_1)^c$ hence $\tau^c = \tau_1^c = \mu(X, X^c)$.

So τ and τ_1 have the same closed sets in X .

3.3 Definition : If (X, τ) is a locally convex space, we will denote by τ^0 the topology on X^c of uniform convergence on the τ -sequentially compact subsets of X .

3.4 Proposition : If (X, τ) is a locally convex space then $\tau^s = \tau^{00}$, where τ^{00} denotes the topology on X of uniform convergence on the τ^0 -sequentially compact subset of X^c .

Proof : In the proposition 3.1, take $Y = X^c$ i.e. consider dual pair (X, X^c) and $\delta = S$ and η the class of τ -equicontinuous subsets of X' . Then $\tau = \tau_\eta$ and $\tau^0 = \tau_\delta$. So every equicontinuous subsets of X' is τ^0 -sequentially compact. Then $\tau \leq \tau^{00}$.

Now take $Y = X^c$ and $\delta = S$ and η the class of τ^0 -sequentially compact subsets of X^c , so every τ -sequentially compact subsets of X is τ^{00} -sequentially compact.

So τ and τ^{00} have the same sequentially compact sets in X .

Now we will show τ^{00} is the finest topology. Let τ_1 is another locally convex topology on X with the same sequentially compact sets as τ . Then by Lemma 3.2 (ii) $(X, \tau)^c = X^c$.

On X^c both the topologies τ^0 and τ_1^0 coincides. So τ^{00} and τ_1^{00} but $\tau_1 \leq \tau_1^{00}$, so $\tau_1 \leq \tau^{00}$. This shows that τ^{00} is the finest locally convex topology on X with the same sequentially compact sets as τ . Hence $\tau^{00} = \tau^s$.

4. Completeness :

Now we will examine completeness of $X^\oplus$ with respect to topology generated by the class of bounded subsets of X .

Let γ be a family of bounded subsets of X , such that $\cup \{A : A \in \gamma\}$ spans X . The uniform convergence topology on X^b on the members of γ will be denoted by τ_γ .

v = the class of sequences in X which are mackey convergent to 0.

λ = the class of τ -null subsequences of a sequence in X .

4.1 Proposition : If $v \leq \gamma$ then (X^b, τ_γ) is complete.

It is by [6] proposition 3.1.

4.2 Proposition : If $\lambda \leq \gamma$ then $X^\oplus$ is a τ_γ -closed subspace of X^b .

Proof : Let $f \in X^\oplus$, which is τ_γ -closure of $X^\oplus$ in X^b , consider a τ -null subsequence of a sequence in X , then there exists $A \in \gamma$ such that $\subseteq A$ since $f \in X^\oplus$ so for any $\varepsilon > 0$ there is $g \in X^\oplus$ such that $f - g$ is a member of $(\varepsilon/2)A$.

Now choose N such that $|\langle x_n, g \rangle| < \varepsilon/2$ for all $n > N$. $|\langle x_n, f \rangle| \leq |\langle x_n, f - g \rangle| + |\langle x_n, g \rangle|$.

So $|\langle x_n, f \rangle| < \varepsilon$ for all $n > N$. Hence $f \in X^\oplus$. So $X^\oplus$ is τ_γ -closed in X^b .

4.3 Theorem : If $\lambda \leq \gamma$ then $X^\oplus$ is a τ_γ -complete subspace of X^b .

Proof : It immediately follows above proposition.

4.4 Definition : Let (X, τ) be locally convex Hausdroff space. We define the family ξ_r in X to be the set of all subsets A of X such that every sequence of points A has a Cauchy subsequence. We define the topology τ^g on X^b to be the topology of uniform convergence on the member of ξ_r .

Define the topology τ^n on X^b to be the topology of uniform convergence on the class of all τ -null subsequences of a sequence in X .

Define the topology τ^0 on X^c to be the topology of uniform convergence on τ -sequentially compact subsets of X .

4.5 Theorem : $X^\oplus$ is complete under each of the topologies τ^n, τ^g, τ^0 and $\beta(X^\oplus, X)$, (where β denotes the strong topology).

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